

CREATING DIGITAL LITERACY SKILLS AWARENESS IN A TECHNOLOGY-DRIVEN SOCIETY: THE NIGERIA'S REALITY

¹Prof. Abraham Oriji (Ph.D; DLS.) and ²Ovwromoh, Blessing Chinwe (Ph.D.)

¹Department of Curriculum Studies & Educational Technology, Faculty of Education, University of PortHarcourt, PortHarcourt, Nigeria.

²Department of Adult and Non-Formal Education, University of PortHarcourt, PortHarcourt, Nigeria.

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Abstract: The 21st century has created a new concept, “digital literacy”, and this idea is of much concern to researchers globally. Today, we are in a society where technology is rapidly advancing, and we cannot claim not to be aware of its potential effects. Technologies determine most of human activities, and have become a part of everyday life, changing the way humans work, organize, communicate, and even relate with others at both the state and international levels; therefore, this has necessitated a new concept of digital literacy that emerged in modern times. Consequently, the overall purpose of this paper is to raise digital awareness, let the public or the uninformed citizen in a rapidly emerging technological age be abreast of the need to be digitally literate to cope with the present realities, especially in Nigeria, through a systematic review of academic literature on the topic. The second purpose is to create digital literacy awareness, where Nigerians will possess the knowledge, skills, and confidence to flourish in the digital world. Additionally, the paper will have an in-depth review of the benefits and challenges of creating digital literacy awareness in the present-day society. Besides, the researchers will consider not failing to make suggestions or recommendations where appropriate for effective digital literacy awareness in a technology-driven society.

Keywords: Digital literacy skills, Digital learning, ICTs in education, AI-driven instruction, Digital citizen, and Empathy.

Introduction

Currently, we live in a time where technology is rapidly advancing, especially since COVID-19 has brought the attention of everyone worldwide to technology and digitalization (Bashar & Naaz, 2024). Reddy, Chaudhary and Hussein (2023) also revealed that the ongoing proliferation of digital technology and services has led individuals to be either digitally included or excluded. The scholars assert that individuals who are not digitally literate have a higher tendency to not be able to handle the various domains of their lives, consequently increasing the likelihood of struggling to participate and survive in the digital world.

Chigbundu and Oluwabiya (2023) revealed that being digitally literate is more than having the ability to interact with a device, but also includes having cognitive (logical reasoning, working memory, paying attention to details, etc.), sociological (effective communication, listening, adhering to ethics, etc.), and emotional skills needed for self-awareness, self-regulation, self-motivation, etc., to act effectively in the digital world.

This has given rise to the growing use of digital technologies, digital platforms, and technology-enabled services, thereby raising the need for citizens to possess relevant digital literacy skills to carry out their designated tasks effectively. We cannot afford to forget the importance of developing digital literacy skills as technology becomes more and more integrated into individuals' daily lives (Bashar & Naaz, 2024). Hence, there is a need for citizens to develop digital skills and competences, and possess relevant digital literacy skills to carry out their designated tasks effectively (Reddy, Sharma & Chaudhary, 2020; Pinto, Sales, Pascual & Mariscal, 2020, and Feerrar, 2019). Reddy, Chaudhary and Hussein (2023) posit that growing demands from the work sector for individuals to be digitally literate have prompted targeted interventions and innovations from the education sector to instill digital skills into the future workforce. Reddy et al (2023) revealed that despite efforts, the digital skills gap remains visible globally. Creating digital literacy skills has become essential for today's world; therefore, there is a need to build a digitally literate Nigeria, where all citizens can improve their lives through the effective use of technology and also contribute to the nation's development.

There is no doubt that the Internet technology relies basically on written communication, where youngsters may lash out at online communities with verbal or text-based comments intended to hurt someone's feelings, and not respond as they would over the phone or in a face-to-face conversation (Council of Europe, 2020). These virtual or computer-based interactions are usually misinterpreted by people, especially as it is not always possible to observe an individual's facial expressions, hear somebody's tone of voice, and understand others' non-verbal cues or body language as observed in face-to-face interactions. In this case, since people cannot easily understand non-verbal signals, it becomes very important for people in online communities to understand that people make and take hasty decisions and harsh judgments instead of giving thoughtful decisions on issues.

Consequently, there is a need for Nigerian citizens to be aware of the dangers of the online environment and empower them by giving them the means to acquire the technical and functional skills and competences required for a democratic culture (Council of Europe, 2020). It has also become very pertinent to protect the safety of Nigerian citizens online and enable them to tackle the major challenges and risks that may arise from the digital environment and emerging technologies (Council of Europe, 2020). Additionally, there is a need to enlighten Nigerian children, not only adults, on the greater educational opportunities inherent in digital education and ensure that all citizens benefit fully from the digital revolution in modern times (Council of Europe, 2020). Furthermore, there is a need to also remind educators and policymakers of the significance of setting digital literacy awareness as a priority for the Nigerian citizens to navigate through the internet for all purposes.

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culture (Council of Europe, 2020). It has also become very pertinent to protect the safety of citizens online and enable them to tackle the major challenges and risks that may arise from the digital environment and emerging technologies (Council of Europe, 2020). Furthermore, there is a need to enlighten our children on the greater educational opportunities inherent in digital education and ensure that all citizens benefit fully from the digital revolution in modern times (Council of Europe, 2020). Again, to remind educators and policymakers of the significance of setting digital citizenship education as a priority

Literature Review

With the digitalization of almost everything in our everyday life or activities, this draws a lot of significant implications, not only to individuals, but to every aspect of human endeavour, which encompasses educators, learners, educational arena, organizations, parastatals, groups, clubs, and associations. In the education sector, we are aware of the recent proliferation of digital devices in our environments and educational software (Pangrazio, Godhe, and Ledesma, 2020), many educators and educational institutions are still grappling with on how to integrate these advanced technologies into the curriculum and prepare their students for the futuristic learning. Noting that the futuristic learning demands on digital skills and/or “digital literacy”, it has become a major concern for educators, researchers, and the stakeholders involved in education industry. To start with, let us define some of the major terms as it will appear in this write-up.

Definition of Terms/Phrases

Digital literacy: The term “digital literacy” came to the limelight in the United States of America in the year 1997, and traced to the publication of Paul Gilster in his book “Digital Literacy”. According to Pangrazio, Godhe, and Ledesma (2020), Gilster’s landmark publication first defined the skills needed to critically navigate information in contemporary time. Digital literacy refers to the basic knowledge, skills, and attitudes that an individual must possess to use digital technologies competently, safely, and appropriately (NDLF, 2023). The UNESCO Institute for Static 2018 defines digital literacy as "the ability to manage, understand, integrate, communicate, evaluate, and create information safely and appropriately through digital technologies for employment, decent jobs, and entrepreneurship." It includes the proficiencies which are referred to as information literacy, computer literacy, and ICT literacy. Additionally, digital literacy is nothing but how effectively interact with digital technology. Digital literacy skills entail the ability to connect an electronic device to the internet, ability to download digital documents online, ability to install software, ability to navigate through e-learning platforms, etcetera (Chigbundu & Oluwabiyi (2023). It also the ability to navigate through a digital tool, ability to search for information using the digital tool, ability to create more devices, and ability to evaluate the digital tool (Chigbundu & Oluwabiyi (2023). The scholars further explained that it also means the ability to organize, access and disseminate information using ICTs.

Digital Citizen: A digital citizen is somebody that uses the internet regularly, brilliantly, collaboratively, and effectively interacts and performs other online tasks with online communities as people that participates or contributes in real-life or conventional communities. A digital citizen is a person who is independent, self-

confident, and skilled on the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) tools to participate in economic, educational, cultural, social, religious, and other activities with online communities.

Digital Citizenship Ethics: This refers to fairness, respecting others' rights, and fostering technology goodness (Birgit, 2021). It also to the set of moral principles guiding responsible, safe, and respectful behavior in digital spaces, focusing on rights, responsibilities, and the impact of online actions, encompassing respect for privacy, intellectual property, truth, and promoting inclusivity and well-being in the digital world. It also focuses on avoiding misinformation, and understanding the legal or social impact of online actions to contribute positively to digital communities. Digital citizenship ethics is not just being a user, it is about being a thoughtful participant, understanding how to act lawfully, safely, and ethically online to build a positive digital community. It is about applying offline morality to the online community, encompassing critical thinking, digital literacy, and empathy for others (<https://www.google.com/search?q=Digital+Citizenship+Ethics+refers+to+the+responsible%2C>). Finally, it refers to fairness, respecting others' rights, and fostering technology goodness (Birgit, 2021); it is about being skilled and protecting personal data, understanding digital rights and responsibilities, and mindful and respecting other persons making informed, positive contributions in digital communities or cyberworld.

Digital Citizenship: This refers to a set of skills, traits, and behaviors that allow people to make use of the benefits and opportunities that the internet provides while also creating resilience to possible risks (Pandian & Balasubramaniam, 2023). Digital citizenship also refers to the responsible use of technology by anyone who uses computers, the internet, and other technologies to engage with society at all levels. Digital citizenship also means "good digital citizenship". It involves being a productive, respectful member of the digital community. (<https://www.anthonywayneschools.org/Downloads/2022-04%20INFO%20AWJH%20Digital%20Citizenship%20Guide.pdf>).

Digital Divide: The term gained recognition in technology as it was first coined in the mid-1990s (Vartanova & Gladkova, 2019). It is about unequal access and distribution of technology among individuals. It refers to the gap between individuals with access to digital technologies and those without, and the unequal distribution of skills and knowledge related to using these technologies. It involves individuals access to technology and the ability to use it effectively (Ramsetty & Adams, 2020). Digital divide means that some individuals or communities have limited or no access to digital resources and technology. This lack of access and skillful use of technologies by individuals have delayed their ability to develop digital competencies (Chama & Subaveerapandiyan, 2023).

Citizenship: According to ChatGPT (2025), this word ordinarily refers to the legal status and relationship between an individual and a state, granting certain rights to vote, duties, privileges, etc. However, citizenship in this paper means the active participation of individuals in social, political, and cultural life of a digital community, promoting shared values and responsibilities.

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of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools to participate in economic, educational, cultural, social, religious, and other activities with online communities.

Empathy: This refers to the ability to understand and share the feelings of others. It enables people to critical understanding how people talk and behave on the internet/online in view of the fact that Internet use depends mostly on written communication. The knowledge and understanding of empathy become very essential because internet users frequently make harsh and/or hasty decisions or judgments because it is very difficult to understand others non-verbal cues as observed during face-to-face interactions. People hardly pause to put themselves in the other person's shoes. Teenagers or youths use the internet mostly; hence, they must understand the meaning of empathy so that they will not use harsh verbal or text-based comments that will hurt someone's feelings. The knowledge of empathy among youths is very vital in order for them to treat others with respect as it happens during face-to-face interactions.

Relationship: According to Jaeger (2021), a relationship is usually conceptualized as citizenship. It is the way two or more persons, groups, countries, talk to, behave towards, and deal with each other. It is the way things are connected, or involving feelings, behaviors, or interactions, ranging from family or friendships to romantic or professional ties, and even abstract connections like cause-and-effect between ideas or events. It signifies a state of being related or interrelated, highlighting shared attributes, influence, or association (https://www.google.com/search?q=DEFINE%3ARELATIONSHIP&oq=DEFINE%3ARELATIONSHIP&gs_lcrp=). A good example of relationship, academically, is that between a teacher and students, where each effects the other.

Human or social relationship could also be the bond between friends, family members, or partners (<https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/relationship#h1>).

Digital Learning: Digital learning refers to the use of a combination of technology, digital content, and instruction to enhance the educational experience. It is an educational approach using technology, like computers, tablets, and the internet, to facilitate teaching and acquiring knowledge, encompassing online courses, virtual classrooms, apps, videos, and interactive tools for flexible, engaging, and personalized experiences. It is an educational approach that uses technology and digital tools, such as educational apps, virtual classrooms, online courses, videos, to deliver instruction. It offers flexibility, personalized experiences, and broader access to learning materials beyond traditional settings. Digital Learning facilitates instruction vial both fully online and blended or hybrid modes. It offers real-time feedback, and uses varied formats, from short microlearning modules to immersive simulations.

Digital Literacy Skills: It is the ability of individuals to effectively understand and use digital technologies for meaningful actions within life situations. It is the ability to access the computer, mobile technologies and the internet for day-to-day activities, and being connected with others on the internet. A digital literate skill person should be able to locate, evaluate, and effectively use information from digital sources, and as well distinguish credible information from the net to avoid misinformation. He should have the knowledge of software, hardware,

and digital tools needed to perform various tasks on the internet, and also analyze digital content, question assumptions, and make informed decisions. Additionally, he should be able to understand cybersecurity, the risks of hacking and data breaches; how to protect personal and professional information, think critically and be abreast of artificial intelligence, which is increasingly important in a cyber world with abundant digital information, and finally collaborate online, ensuring digital safety, and adapting to new technologies (https://www.google.com/search?q=Whai+is+Digital+Literacy+Skills&oq=Whai+is+Digital+Literacy+Skills&gs_lcrp=).

ICT in Education: ICT (Information and Communication Technology). ICT in education refers to the use of or the application of technological tools to the teaching-learning process in education. It involves using digital tools like computers, internet, apps, and smartboards to enhance teaching-learning by making it more interactive, accessible, and engaging through digital resources, online platforms, and communication tools, moving beyond traditional methods to personalized and collaborative experience (https://www.google.com/search?q=Difine+ICTs+in+education&sca_esv=513b073ce7aced3&ei=). It involves the use of Smartboards for interactive lessons, online platforms, such a Google classroom, e-learning systems, educational apps and Software for self-paced learning and content delivery. It integrates communication tolls such as email, video conferencing for student-teacher interaction. Additionally, digital Resources, such as e-textbooks, videos, animations, virtual reality simulations are not excluded.

AI-driven instruction: AI-driven instruction refers to the use of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies to personalize and enhance the learning experience for students. This approach utilizes AI algorithms to analyze student data, adapt educational content, and provide personalized feedback, ultimately aiming to improve learning outcomes and engagement. (<https://www.google.com/search?q=AI-driven+instruction>

Digitalization: Digitization, according to Ogunode and Ndayebom (2023) is conceptualized as those facilities that aid the conversion of teaching and learning into platforms like online courses, online assessments, and web seminars/conferences or workshops through the use of electronic platforms. Micheal and Jacob (2017) also defined digitization as the process of converting educational resources from material forms to electronic forms where they can be stored and manipulated by a computer. Digitalization is the process of transforming physical teaching and learning resources into packages, platforms, or electronic forms where they can be stored and manipulated by a computer for the implementation of teaching and learning programmes in school. Bejinaru (2019) defined digitalization as the conversion of text, pictures, video, and music into digital format utilizing technologies, such as laptop computers, the internet, mobile devices, scanners, digital cameras, projectors, and printers, etc., that may be played by computers.

The Relevance of Digital Literacy Awareness in Nigeria

Technology is continually imparting every person all over the world; so also has every job and career, every field of study, even social and personal lives are increasingly impacted by technology (Abdullahi & Alo, 2023). Without exaggeration, all nations are presently competing in today's global world, and have digitally invested

their economies. For Nigeria to cope with this competitiveness of this digital economy, and to level the playing field, it must move its citizens to a greater competitive position in the global economic marketplace. No doubt, in today's connected world, as applauded by (Agaka, 2024), digital literacy is the pillar that empowers individuals, communities, and nations to handle the challenges of the digital era. A digital literacy standard for Nigeria will prepare Nigerians to meet the challenge of inadequacies in digital literacy and skills acquisition (Abdullahi & Alo, 2023).

National Digital Economy Policy and Strategy (NDEPS) has emphasized that digital literacy is a global priority and criterion for employment with over 1.5 billion current virtual workforce vacancies across the world. In concord with NDEPS, James (2024) opined thus: "As industries become more reliant on technology, ensuring that adults possess the skills to navigate digital platforms is crucial for improving employability, productivity, and innovation". In the same vein, the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2019), revealed that workers with strong digital skills are more likely to find employment, earn higher wages, and adapt to changes in the labor market.

As the case may be, according to NDEPS, the competence in English language is no longer the primary indicator of literacy and job readiness; it is now digital literacy. Consequently, digital literacy awareness must be created in Nigeria. Nigerians must be equipped with relevant digital literacy skills to keep up with best global practices, and place the current workers, youths, and other professionals in ready mode for opportunities that may open within and beyond the Nigerian shores. This, as (Abdullahi & Alo, 2023) revealed, will diversify the economy, significantly reduce unemployment and enhance labour productivity and mobility.

Below are the stated purposes or the needs for digital literacy awareness in Nigeria, especially in teaching and learning situations: -

- i. Nigerians current workforce, students, graduates, and professionals need to be prepared for successful adulthood in a world increasingly saturated with digital technologies; Nigerians are already engaging with digital technologies and digital media and using them to find information and communicate meaning in different modes and formats, which provides significant opportunities and challenges that are important to address;
- ii. Not all Nigerians are equally equipped with the skills, knowledge and understanding that will allow them to critically engage with technology and to use it well;
- iii. Developing digital literacy can help students to access subject knowledge at a time when digital technologies are changing the way knowledge is created and communicated;
- iv. Digital literacy will help schools to engage with students lived experiences and existing knowledge as well as extending and diversifying these experiences and knowledge to make learning more relevant and purposeful;
- v. There is need to create a pool of knowledgeable and skilled manpower that will facilitate technology acquisition, assimilation, diffusion, mobility and raise productivity.

Naaz and Bashar (2024) revealed hereunder how raising citizens level of digital literacy can make a positive difference in every persons' life as citizens can take advantage of the plethora of opportunities available online and navigate the digital landscape with confidence.

- i. By improving digital literacy in Nigeria, the citizens can increase their chances of getting hired or promoted in their current employment.
- ii. Adequate digital literacy awareness will encourage peer cooperation and communication by utilizing digital tools like collaborative writing platforms and online discussion boards.
- iii. Adequate digital literacy will make it much easier to improve digital dialogue by making citizens keep in constant touch with friends and relatives, who live far away, which is impossible ordinarily (conventionally).
- iv. Possessing digital literacy skills will give citizens better access to online seminars, courses, research databases, digital libraries, and information and wealth of knowledge, which cannot be possible conventionally.
- v. Being more digitally literate will make it much easier for a better improved communication by staying in touch with friends and relatives who live far away.
- vi. Greater accessibility to information. Possessing digital literacy skills gives you access to a wealth of information and tools, such as research databases, digital libraries, and online courses.
- vii. Greater production output. This can be especially useful for independent contractors, business owners, and anybody else looking to boost productivity. Acquiring expertise in digital tools and platforms can increase output and enable you to finish jobs more quickly
- viii. Since the integration of digital technologies are being used often in field of education learners would like to acquire strong digital literacy to succeed in their academic endeavours.

Naaz, and Bashar (2024) justified the importance of digital literacy in the classroom thus:

- (1). Information accessibility
 - (2). Teamwork and communication
 - (3). Critical thinking and problem-solving
 - (4). Cyber safety and responsible usage
 - (5). Training and education throughout life
 - (6). Increase digital equity
- Digital Literacy is critical to immediate empowerment of the population to enable Nigerians to develop the skills necessary to achieve more, to be distinguished and advance in the digital era and to truly solve the conundrum (challenges) around education, unemployment, low productivity, and economic diversification (Abdullahi & Alo, 2023).

Contemporary Challenges of Creating Digital Literacy Awareness in Nigeria.

Nigeria's aspiration to attain 95 per cent digital literacy by 2030 highlights a thoughtful commitment to equipping its citizens with the skills and knowledge necessary to thrive in the digital (Agaka, 2024). The Federal Government of Nigeria through the National Digital Economy Policy and Strategy and Chigbundu and Oluwabiyi, (2023) affirmed that creating digital literacy awareness in Nigeria faces several significant challenges. Listed below are some of the major challenges.

1. inadequate funding (2). limited access to infrastructure and resources (3) affordability issues (4). lack of qualified personnel (5). resistance to change (6). the uneven distribution of digital access between urban and rural areas (7). the need to integrate digital literacy into the formal education system are also major hurdles.

Agaka (2024) and others affirmed that the journey to create digital literacy awareness in Nigeria is not devoid of hurdles, which need to be addressed for the vision to be realized. The hurdles are:

1. Infrastructure barriers (that is, those in urban centers often enjoy better connectivity and access to digital tools than their rural counterparts). One of the main issues is the lack of access to digital infrastructure, particularly in rural areas (Naaz & Bashar, 2024). Affordability of digital devices. The cost of digital devices, such as computers and smartphones, to be used to attain digital literacy, is unaffordable for many Nigerians. While the digital age has ushered in a wealth of opportunities, the expenses associated with acquiring computers and smartphones serve as a challenge, particularly for those in the lower-income bracket.

2. Urban-rural technology differences & educational landscape: One of the contemporary challenges of creating digital literacy awareness in Nigeria is the issue of rural and urban differences, whereby those in urban areas are more connected to the internet and have more access to electricity than those in the rural areas, who may not have even seen electric pole for once, have no access to digital tools, and may not be connected to the internet.

3. Socio-economic factors (i.e., affordability of digital devices). If somebody has not eaten for survival due to the economic realities biting very hard in Nigerian today, how would the person purchase or afford to buy any of the digital devices? (Tiwari & Sahoo, 2025) have told us that slow or unstable internet service creates one of the major barriers for all, especially in rural, remote, or economically disadvantaged regions.

4. Awareness and perceptions surrounding digital literacy (requires refined strategies to dispel myths and create an understanding of its transformative potential).

5. The spread of misinformation on the internet is very rampant, and somebody may believe such news to be true. Without proper guidance, students and other learners may find it very difficult to distinguish trustworthy or reliable information from misinformation on the Internet or online, which may definitely and possibly lead to the spread of false or misleading content.

6. The challenge of digital literacy awareness initiatives may expose some individuals to inappropriate or unfortunate content or information, which, if believed may put someone into trouble.

7. Integrating digital literacy awareness into the formal educational system may also create more problems for the citizens. Many educational institutions in Nigeria lack the necessary infrastructure, such as computers, educational software, and other facilities to facilitate meaningful digital education.

8. Update of relevant educational content is often very rare where schools do have access to these resources.

9. Furthermore, adding digital learning to the curriculum largely depends on how skilled educators are in using these tools. Regrettably, many teachers lack the necessary training to seamlessly include digital tools in their teaching methods. The fast-paced changes in technology make this challenge even more difficult, as educators find it challenging to keep up with the latest advancements.

10. Infrastructure issue is a big problem: One of the main issues is the lack of access to digital infrastructure (Chigbundu & Oluwabiyi, 2023), lack of smart phones to access the net, particularly in Nigerian rural areas. To improve digital literacy, a suitable infrastructure, such as a computer, energy, internet connectivity, etc. are needed to be purchased.

11. Over-reliance or dependency on technology is yet another problem arising from digital literacy awareness. It may become impossible for individuals to perform some functions or activities without the use of technological devices or tools. Extreme dependence on digital tools may hamper the progress of other sectors that are vital non-digital skills, such as hands-on experience, critical thinking, problem-solving, etc. In the educational arena, this over-reliance on technology have often made some students and teachers very vulnerable to technical issues. This may include system failures, the internet outages, which often disrupt students learning and teachers research or work processes. Additionally, over-dependence on digital communication may lead to social isolation, resulting to a decrease in face-to-face interactions, which will potentially impact social skills and emotional development among citizens.

12. Digital distractions have been established to be one of the challenges of digital literacy awareness. It has been identified to distract students reading at home (Chigbundu & Oluwabiyi, 2023). The issues of online environments and digital devices (Facebook sounds, WhatsApp, and telephones ringing.) can be highly distracting, which most often leads to reduced students' attention spans and difficulty focusing on their academic responsibilities.

There are several online risks that may arise from digital literacy awareness. Such risks may include cyberbullying and other forms of risks on the Internet.

13. Digital divide has also been identified as one of the challenges of digital literacy awareness. The issue of inequalities in access and skills, especially those individuals that live in the remote areas of the country. Presently in Nigeria, there is noticeable digital divide among the citizens. Therefore, focusing on promoting digital literacy awareness may worsen the existing digital divide, particularly if nothing is done to address the broader economic inequalities in the society or amongst Nigerians. A report by the UK Department for Education (2020) noted that digital skills gaps persist, particularly among older adults and those in lower-income brackets, limiting their ability to fully participate in the digital economy. This is not different from Nigerian situation today.

14. Eye problem also constitutes yet another challenge, which is caused by frequent exposure of the eye to bright light (Chigbundu & Oluwabiyi, 2023).

Generally, digital literacy awareness has a lot of consequences. It may unintentionally expose citizens to inapt or irrelevant content online, such as cyberbullying, harassment, hate speech, pornography, violence, and other online cheats or scams. These experiences can be emotionally destructive and create an undesirable online environment, especially among the youths and adults.

Solutions to Improve the Knowledge of Digital Literacy Awareness in Nigeria

In today's world, you cannot claim or think of being digitally illiterate; if you are, you must think of becoming digital literate. One cannot afford to be digitally illiterate in today's world (i.e., technology age), where being knowledgeable about digital tools or devices will make a lot of positive difference by taking the advantages and lots of opportunities available on the Internet to navigate the digital landscape with confidence throughout one's lifetime.

Happily, the researchers were intimated from literature that the Federal Government of Nigeria through the National Digital Economy Policy and Strategy (NDEPS) document has set a target for achieving 95 per cent digital literacy by 2030 (Abdullahi & Alo, 2023). And the National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA), the body responsible for developmental regulation of the sector in Nigeria, has also taken up the responsibility to lead the development of a National Digital Literacy Framework (Abdullahi & Alo, 2023). Nigerian citizens are sure that if honestly and fully implemented the later, the sky will be the limit, and Nigerians will happily and easily navigate the web with ease.

However, the National Digital Literacy Framework (NDLF), Agaka (2024), and others have outlined the major ways in which to improve digital literacy awareness for Nigerians.

1. government should set community technology centers that are equipped with computers, other digital devices, and internet access for the citizens.
2. exploring e-waste recycling programmes, which he claimed can be a sustainable approach. He suggested repurposing and redistributing refurbished devices will make digital tools affordable for a broader segment of the population.
3. Vigorous campaign should be mounted by the government for the public to create digital literacy awareness, and this will draw the citizens closer to the benefits of digital literacy. The opportunity should also be used to inform the populace the potential risks associated with using the internet, and as well enlighten them of safe online behavior or conduct, responsible internet use, and data privacy, which is supposed to be the primary goal of these campaigns (Naaz & Bashar, 2024).
4. Policy implementation is yet another challenge. another crucial step is the implementing policies that will subsidize cost of digital devices for low-income individuals.
5. Government-backed initiatives or collaborations with private sector entities can help make devices more accessible.
6. Agaka (2024) made the following suggestion to assist kids in developing their digital literacy by making use of the digital libraries and online courses that universities offer in addition to other digital resources.
 - i. To manage and arrange assignments, make use of digital tools like to-do lists and online calendars.
 - ii. To scan a document, or a few pages from a textbook using digital technologies to help reduce the amount of paper clutter.
7. Naaz and Bashar (2024) suggested that to improve digital literacy awareness, a suitable infrastructure, such as a computer, energy, and internet connectivity are needed, specifically in rural areas where increased

internet speed is explicitly needed. To overcome this, there is need to invest in network infrastructure, such as, National Optical Fiber Network (Naaz & Bashar, 2024).

8. Again, Naaz and Bashar (2024) identified the absence or lack of trained or professional personnel on digital service sector, which poses a big challenge to digital literacy awareness. Where this exist, they are quacks or half-backed. To overcome the challenge, professional or trained personnel should be employed for the maintenance of the digital devices they managed to provide.

9. There is a need for government to plan for public awareness initiatives to enlighten and teach the citizens about the benefits of digital literacy in a knowledge-age society, and as well as any intimating the populace on the potential risks associated with using the internet. Therefore, increasing public knowledge of safe online conduct, responsible internet use, and data privacy is a must (Naaz and Bashar, 2024), which will form the primary goal of the campaign.

10. Socioeconomic Disparities: There are prominent socioeconomic differences in Nigeria that need to be addressed. You cannot use what you do not have. Digital technologies (equipment and materials) are limited to many individuals in Nigeria, and this is due to financial inability. Again, most of the institutions in Nigeria are yet to introduce digital literacy courses in their curriculum.

11. Basic Education: There is a saying that states that illiteracy is a common disease. Of a truth, many Nigerians need basic literacy, because it will be very challenging for citizens who have no basic education to interact with digital technology, materials or software if they cannot read and write.

12. Nigerian government should invest in digital infrastructure by investing in network connectivity, specifically in rural or remote areas where network connectivity is very poor or not available (Bashar & Naaz, 2024).

13. Since Nigeria has plethora of local languages, it will be proper to localized languages and content in different languages to cater for the diverse linguistic populace, particular for those citizens who may not speak English very well, but can read in their local languages, for instance, Ibo, Haus and Yoruba languages could go a long way to addressing the issue. This, if practiced, could promote digital literacy proficiency awareness (Bashar & Naaz, 2024).

14. Over reliance on technology is another demerit of digital literacy use in everyday life. When the citizens potential over-rely on technology, this becomes a problem to them because there is nothing, they will do without depending on technology. Excessive reliance on digital tools can hinder the development of crucial non-digital skills like critical thinking, problem-solving, and hands-on experience. Over-dependence on technology can make individuals vulnerable to technical issues, such as internet outages or system failures, disrupting learning or work processes (<https://www.google.com/search?q=disadvantages+of+creating+digital+litracy+awareness>).

15. Digital distraction is yet other problem of digital literacy. Cases are evident where students' phones ring in the class or during study periods and their studies are abandoned to answer the phone calls, or give reply to the text messages as the case may be. Therefore, Digital devices and online environments can constantly distract

individuals, thereby leading to decreased attention spans and difficulty focusing on tasks. This can negatively impact academic performance and productivity. (<https://www.google.com/search?q=disadvantages+of+creating+digital+litracy+awareness>).

16. There are lots of misinformation on the Internet. The information posted on the net are never edited as experienced in journal articles, which are usually peer reviewed. Any person can post anything on the internet because the news or the information posted on the net are never edited. Without proper guidance, individuals may struggle to discern credible information from misinformation online, potentially leading to the spread of false or misleading content (<https://www.google.com/search?q=disadvantages+of+creating+ digital+litracy+awareness>).

17. Additionally, digital literacy awareness initiatives may expose individuals to inappropriate content and online risks, such as cyberbullying, pornography, violence, and hate speech, harassment, and online scams. which is one of the risks usually encountered on the net (<https://www.google.com/search?q=disadvantages+of+creating+digital+litracy+awareness>).

18. Government should introduce a special course titled “teaching digital competencies” in secondary schools to groom them young.

Summary

This paper focused and discussed on creating digital literacy skills awareness in a technology-driven society based on Nigeria’s present realities. The authors tried to give meanings to some major pertinent terms or phrases that are relevant to the topic under discussion. The authors have also reminded Nigerian citizens the relevance of digital literacy awareness in this cyberworld, and to be prepared to be digitally skilled to navigate the internet effectively. The scholars also informed Nigerian citizens and highlighted the contemporary relevance and challenges of creating digital literacy awareness among Nigerians. At the same time, they recommended and meticulously discussed some vital solutions to improve the knowledge of digital literacy awareness in Nigeria.

Conclusion

There is no doubt that the knowledge of digital literacy awareness in Nigeria is very vital to sustain her economic growth in a knowledge-based society. The ability to navigate through the internet safely and control the digital technologies will become a prerequisite for Nigerian citizens, particularly in the area of employment. Although, based on literature, digital literacy awareness in Nigeria is still at its neophyte stage, as there remains substantial disparities in technology access and proficiency, particularly among the lower-income groups. Seriously, there is a need to significantly improve the situation (i.e., disparities in access and proficiency in use), principally among the youths, older adults, and lower-income groups. Hence, since digital literacy contributes to a long-term economic sustainability in any nation, Nigerian policymakers, industry leaders, and curriculum planners should collaborate to include digital literacy awareness into the curriculum. For a sustainable and dynamic workforce, capable of thriving in the digital economy, according to James (2023), there is a need for a resilient or robust and ultimate promotion of digital literacy awareness among Nigerian citizens to properly navigate into the digital or cyberworld.

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